

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Mechanisms of production management within the framework of strategic development play a pivotal role in fostering economic growth. Numerous researchers have contributed to the development of this field.

For instance, A. A. Asaul and his colleagues (2014) emphasized the necessity of adopting innovative approaches in their research on strategic management of production processes. They highlighted the importance of analyzing internal and external factors comprehensively when shaping strategies to ensure organizational stability.

R. Kaplan and D. Norton (1996) introduced the “Balanced Scorecard” concept, proposing a comprehensive approach to strategic management. They argued that organizations should not rely solely on financial metrics to improve efficiency but also focus on critical aspects like customer relations and internal processes. This framework has become a widely used strategic tool in production management.

G. Mintzberg (1987) explored various approaches to strategic management and developed the “Five Ps for Strategy” concept. He stressed the significance of balancing rigid and adaptive methods in strategic planning for enterprises, which is vital for managing production effectively.

Among local researchers, T. Tursunov (2019) has paid special attention to the issues of strategic production management in Uzbekistan. His studies underline the positive impact of technological innovations and state-created favorable conditions on the local industrial sectors.

E. Porter (1990), in his “Competitive Advantage of Nations” theory, underscored the importance of strategic production management in enhancing national competitiveness. He asserted that countries must focus on integrating advanced technologies and developing a highly skilled workforce to build a competitive economy.

These works provide a solid theoretical and practical foundation for understanding strategic production management mechanisms. Applying these insights to Uzbekistan’s context can enhance the strategic approaches used by local enterprises. In particular, leveraging international best practices in innovation and optimizing production processes can contribute significantly to the sustainable growth of the national economy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology combines qualitative and quantitative approaches. Primary data were collected through interviews and surveys with industry experts and enterprise managers, focusing on the application and effectiveness of production management strategies. Secondary data were sourced from academic publications, government reports, and industry analyses. Data were analyzed using thematic coding for qualitative insights and statistical methods for quantitative trends, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the topic.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Uzbekistan has achieved significant success in the development of the regional manufacturing sector. Among these achievements are the creation and enhancement of the competitiveness of industries and the establishment of favorable conditions for developing new fields. With regard to the industrial complex of Uzbekistan, this necessitates further development and modernization of regional competitiveness in productive sectors through the in-depth introduction of advanced technologies into the economy.

A successful strategy for the sustainable development of the domestic economy depends primarily on an objective assessment of actual conditions and the development of new methodological approaches to understanding the competitiveness of the economic system and its control mechanisms. The strategy identifies five priority areas:

- Reform of public administration;
- Reform of the judiciary and strengthening the rule of law;
- Economic development and liberalization;
- The social sector;
- Security and foreign policy [3].

A systematic methodological approach, based on recognizing the competitive market environment, is adequate as an imperative for different economic systems. This approach accounts for the effects of all factors on the sustainable development of the economy to construct a complete system of national economic modernization. These trends, against the backdrop of a changing world order, bring to the forefront issues of liberalizing economic systems and utilizing national competitive advantages to modernize the economy.

As a result, priority tasks for expanding exports have been defined in the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis. It is necessary to ensure the timely and high-quality implementation of roadmaps for agreements reached during high-level visits to Central Asian states, as well as to China, Russia, South Korea, the United States, Turkey, and other countries that are major partners. Additionally, introducing a

warning system for security threats during customs inspections, abolishing unnecessary licenses and permits issued by customs authorities that do not meet modern requirements, is essential [4].

It is advisable to develop and implement a strategy to increase the export of fruit and vegetable products. Furthermore, the consistent implementation of medium-term programs for reform, structural transformation, and diversification of the economy and its sectors in the first half of the year has ensured the preservation of sustainable high rates of economic growth, macroeconomic balance, and positive dynamics in the main macroeconomic parameters [5].

The concept of the government of Uzbekistan is for the country to reach the level of industrialized nations by the middle of this century. Essential elements of this transformation include:

- Firstly, improving the efficiency and competitiveness of the economy and reducing dependence on the export of a number of commodities;
- Secondly, strengthening the financial sector to support self-employment;
- Thirdly, diversifying production, aimed at increasing the output of goods and services with higher added value, which can demonstrate comparative advantages;
- Fourthly, creating new jobs for the rapidly growing number of educated young people;
- Fifthly, improving management practices to enhance the efficiency of industrial development;
- Sixthly, improving the efficiency of public administration, including better access to information about government policies and the results of their implementation.

As a result, Uzbekistan's GDP growth is expected to maintain momentum, with projections of 5.7% growth for both 2025 and 2029. Inflation is anticipated to moderate, with forecasts suggesting a decline to approximately 9.4% by 2025, as the government continues its modernization efforts.

In 2023, Uzbekistan adopted the National Development Strategy until 2030 ("Uzbekistan-2030"). Among its goals is achieving upper-middle-income status by the end of this decade. The country's priorities include expanding opportunities for citizens' development, ensuring the population's well-being through sustainable economic growth, protecting the environment and natural resources, and developing public services with a focus on people's needs [6].

Active investment is being made in raising human capital in the education, health, and physical training sectors.

During the years of independence, there has been a gradual reduction in the share of agriculture in the GDP structure, which is connected to the further expansion of the potential for developing industries and services. At the same time, the decline in the share of agriculture in GDP occurred against the backdrop of positive average annual growth rates of agricultural products.

Table 1. Uzbekistan: Key Economic Indicators, 2024.

Components	Last	Previous	Unit	Reference
GDP from Agriculture	98977.90	26429.80	UZS Billion	Jun 2024
GDP from Construction	33200.30	13001.70	UZS Billion	Jun 2024
GDP from Manufacturing	117931.80	50422.70	UZS Billion	Jun 2024
GDP from Services	39278.70	18789.60	UZS Billion	Jun 2024

Source: World Bank.

The competitiveness of industries in Uzbekistan is influenced by several factors. One of the key challenges is the high level of material costs in production, which impacts the overall efficiency and profitability of enterprises. Additionally, the energy intensity of industrial product production in Uzbekistan exceeds the global average, posing a significant barrier to competitiveness. Another critical issue is the high degree of wear and tear on main production assets. This is exacerbated by insufficient funding for research and innovation, which limits the ability to modernize processes and implement technical and technological updates necessary for industrial production.

Despite these challenges, several factors contribute positively to the competitiveness of the modernization industry in Uzbekistan. The availability of a skilled and low-cost workforce provides a strong foundation for industrial development. Moreover, the country has a long-standing tradition in textile production, supported by the availability of high-quality raw materials such as cotton and yarn. The stable supply of energy, including gas and electricity, along with well-developed infrastructure, further strengthens the industrial base. State support in the form of privileges, preferences, and a favorable investment environment has been instrumental in attracting investments and fostering growth. Access to major markets, particularly the CIS countries, enhances the export potential of Uzbek industries. Additionally, the high level of cooperation between industries and other sectors of the economy, such as agriculture, engineering, finance, and logistics, creates a synergistic effect that supports

competitiveness. International participation in the global division of labor, along with foreign investment and foreign trade, has also played a crucial role in enhancing the competitive position of Uzbekistan's industries.

To sustain and enhance the competitiveness of key sectors such as machine building, light industry, food production, and the fuel and energy complex, Uzbekistan needs to develop a long-term strategy for socioeconomic development. The main objective of this strategy should be to ensure the country's sustainable development while maintaining its competitiveness on the global stage. This approach will enable Uzbekistan to address existing challenges, capitalize on its strengths, and achieve stable economic growth in the coming years.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Globalization has necessitated the development and implementation of economic policies aimed at maximizing benefits while minimizing risks. To achieve this, a country must: successfully compete in international trade and attract foreign capital; respond quickly and effectively to changes in the international environment. A country facing macroeconomic and structural imbalances and vulnerabilities risks losing the confidence of both domestic and foreign investors, potentially triggering rapid capital outflows. It is equally important to actively protect the rights of domestic and foreign investors through relevant bodies and mechanisms of the WTO and other international organizations [4].

The main directions and targets for structural transformation in the industrial sector to enhance the competitiveness of economic sectors are as follows:

Ensuring structural diversification of the industry based on the development of innovative technologies and the effective transfer of advanced foreign technologies;

Enhancing the competitive advantages of Uzbekistan's industrial sector in traditional industries through product diversification and transitioning from the export of primary commodities to the export of processed products;

Mobilizing internal reserves and opportunities to foster the development of manufacturing industries focused on finished products by improving the competitiveness of the automotive and textile sectors, boosting the capacity of knowledge-intensive industries, machine building, and the chemical industry, and creating new high-tech industries to produce competitive, export-oriented products;

Diversifying export structures and ensuring export growth by increasing the share of finished products with high added value, strengthening the competitive advantages of the light, textile, and food industries;

Systematically addressing the creation of an innovation-oriented, high-tech industrial structure to significantly enhance the competitive potential of the economy. This can be achieved by leveraging comparative advantages in science, education, and the development of scientific and technological capacity, as well as by fostering high technology and tapping into new sources of economic growth;

Accelerating the replacement of obsolete equipment in large enterprises, advancing the modernization of production facilities, and introducing modern, proven technologies available in global markets.

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